

**A Qualitative Study Exploring How People Make Sense of
Microdosing Psychedelics for Mental Health: A Thematic Synthesis**

[2355331]

MSc Mental Health

School of Psychology

University of Birmingham

Abstract

Microdosing of psychedelics for mental health is a novel phenomenon and so, there exists a gap in literature. This research aims to address the research question, “How do people make sense of microdosing psychedelics in relation to mental health?” There has been an increasing interest in psychedelic research in recent years, however as microdosing is a novel phenomenon, there is a gap in literature and studies are scattered, with no thematic synthesis previously conducted exploring the research question. Existing literature was reviewed to inform the rationale, aims and research question. The study conducts a thematic synthesis by systematically exploring and selecting qualitative papers based on the research question and the inclusion and exclusion criteria, which was informed by the PICO framework. Five databases i.e., PubMed, PsycINFO, Web of Science, Scopus and Science Direct, were thoroughly searched using index and free-text terms, without time limitations. The PRISMA guidelines and CASP criteria were used to guide the process and ensure a high standard of quality and standardisation being met. Ten studies were selected to be included in the thematic synthesis and highlighted a broad range of valuable themes and insights essential to address the research question. The themes were categorised into perceived effects and observations, impacts on mental health, psychosocial and general wellbeing, and cognitive functioning for better mental health. Each theme had several key elements, including both positive and negative effects and experiences, and largely overlapped. They also reflected on the variation of subjective experiences and the complexity of the phenomenon. Some key findings were reduced anxiety, depression, and clinical symptoms as well as enhanced mood, sociability, self-perception, mindfulness, and performance etc. However, in certain cases, negative effects such as exacerbation of symptoms and social anxiety were also reported. The research also identified certain gaps and future avenues of research while demonstrating replicable methods and highlighting the importance of qualitative studies to address how people navigate the practice of microdosing psychedelics via perceived and felt effects in relation to mental health.

Table of Contents

Introduction	5
What are Psychedelics?	5
History of Psychedelic Research	5
Microdosing: A Novel Phenomenon	7
Previous Literature on Psychedelic Microdosing	8
Rationale, Research Question and Aims	10
Methodology	12
Selection Criteria	12
Search Strategy	13
Study Selection and Characteristics	16
Analysis & Synthesis	16
Theoretical Orientation	17
Reflexivity	18
Results	20
Making Sense of Microdosing Psychedelics: Perceived Effects	20
Mental Health	22
Psychosocial and General Wellbeing	26
Cognitive Functioning	28
Discussion	32
Findings	32
Evaluation	34
Suggestions for Future Research	37
Conclusion	39
References	41
Appendices	47

Introduction

Microdosing of psychedelics for mental health is a novel phenomenon and so, there exists a gap in literature this research aims to fill. This chapter aims to introduce the concepts of psychedelics and microdosing, present a brief history and prior research as well as identify trends and patterns, interrelationships, experiences, effects, and motivations etc. that derive the rationale, research question and aims of the research project being undertaken.

What are Psychedelics?

Psychedelics refer to a specific class of psychoactive substances due to their complex effects on behaviour, psychology and physiology, and alterations of conscious states via activation of 5-HT_{2A} receptors (Kuypers et al., 2019; Brecksema et al., 2020). These may not be perceived the same way as recreational drugs, rather it may be useful to understand them in terms of their historical context (addressed later in the chapter) as well as their classifications. Psychedelics consist of ‘classic’ serotonergic psychedelics, such as lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD), psilocybin, dimethyltryptamine (DMT) and ayahuasca, and ‘atypical’ psychedelic ibogaine and dissociative anaesthetics, including N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) and ketamine (Brecksema et al., 2020).

History of Psychedelic Research

Natural psychedelic substances, including plants and fungi, have been used in numerous indigenous medicinal and spiritual traditions for thousands of years due to their properties and positive effects on users (Doblin et al., 2019). However, Hofmann's 1938 creation of LSD and subsequent discovery of its effects, characteristics, and possible applications to enhance psychological, social, and biological elements marked the beginning of modern research and interest in psychedelics (Hofmann, 1970). This paved the way for the ‘second wave’ of psychedelics and the establishment of the Journal of Psychedelic Drugs (Smith, 2019), which is now known as the Journal of Psychoactive Drugs and served as a reliable source for psychedelic research during this era and still stands today (Doblin et al., 2019). Though the second wave overlapped with the counterculture of the 1960s, there was a surge in ground-

breaking research, particularly the use of LSD as an experimental therapy for alcoholism and psychiatric illness, such as schizophrenia and depression, leading to the development of SSRIs and research into neurochemistry, as well as the discovery of psilocybin in the sacred mushrooms used by Central American shamans (Smith, 2019).

Despite its academic and pharmacological significance, paired with positive impacts on mental health and wellbeing, cognition, creativity, and physiology, psychedelic research was largely halted for nearly four decades due to legal restrictions and bans on the substances resulting from growing political concern over recreational use, stigma and disbelief or common unacceptance of their benefits (Kuypers et al., 2019; Smith, 2019; Fadiman, 2011).

It wasn't until recently that psychedelic research was revived. According to Fadiman (2011), this was made possible by a new generation of researchers, scientists, and regulators who were curious, open-minded, and more accepting of this previously 'radical' revision, opening the door to further research and development of various aspects in this field. Though psychedelic substances are still considered illegal, there has been a resurgence in controlled macro-dosing laboratory studies and clinical trials, involving both human and animal participants, large-scale population studies and naturalistic studies exploring their effects on behaviour, functioning and mental health, as well as treatment potential either alone or in conjunction to existing interventions (Gregorio et al., 2021; Andersen et al., 2020).

Preliminary reports from contemporary link psychedelics to improved mental health (OCD, depression, anxiety, PTSD, addiction & substance use disorders, suicidal ideation, etc.), cognitive ability, sociability, self-perception, creativity, and chronic physical conditions, such as migraines etc. (Carhart-Harris and Goodwin, 2017; Brekke et al., 2020; Kuypers et al., 2019). One of the first studies to examine how psilocybin affects individuals with treatment-resistant OCD was the Moreno et al. (2006) study. Psilocybin was administered to nine individuals with clinically diagnosed OCD in a double-blind, random manner with regular doses of 100–300 µg/kg and a microdose of 25 µg/kg. The Yale-Brown Obsessive-Compulsive Scale (YBOCS) and a visual-analogue scale that assessed the intensity of OCD symptoms were used in the study to find a decrease in OCD symptoms, which ranged from 23-100%, with 8 out of 9 reporting symptom reduction of ≥25% and 6 out of 9 of ≥50.

Carhart-Harris et al. (2016) conducted another psilocybin investigation to examine the feasibility, safety, and efficacy of administering psilocybin to people with treatment-resistant depression. The open-label feasibility trial was conducted using 12 people with moderate-to-severe, unipolar, treatment-resistant depression and administered oral doses of psilocybin (10 µg and 25 µg) every week, in a supportive setting. Using the Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptoms (QIDS), sustained improvements in anxiety and depression were found in the post-treatment assessments from 1-week to 3-months. Several studies such as Sanches et al. (2016), Gasser et al. (2014), and Griffiths et al. (2016) also explore the effects of using psychedelic substances, like ayahuasca, LSD, and psilocybin, on mental health conditions like depression and anxiety.

There has also been a rise in meta-analysis and systematic reviews being conducted that support these findings by critically and systematically analysing a wide range of research across different disciplines. Studies such as Gregorio et al. (2021), Andersen et al. (2020), Rucker, Iliff and Nutt (2018), Luoma et al. (2020), and Brekke et al. (2020) provide strong evidence as they review a variety of academic literature, including preclinical and clinical trials, randomised control trials, population and discourse analysis, and so on, to provide consistent results regarding the use of psychedelic substances and improvements in mental health via reduced clinical symptoms, therapeutic and prosocial effects, and enhancement of overall wellbeing. However, there remains a gap in literature regarding certain aspects of psychedelic use and its impacts, e.g., long-term effects, variations in settings, etc., highlighting the need for future research.

Microdosing: A Novel Phenomenon

Microdosing is a novel phenomenon in the field of psychedelic research. It has been loosely described as a dose that is 1% of the pharmacologically active psychedelic drug dose, up to a maximum of 100 µg, though there is a lack of scientific consensus (Kuypers et al., 2019; Rootman et al., 2021). Thus, a psychedelic microdose typically lies between 1/10th-1/20th of a psychoactive or recreational dose, varying within and between substances, and doesn't cause intoxication or altered consciousness, rather subtle but observable positive effects through repeated dosing sessions undertaken with the intention to improve wellbeing, cognitive and/or emotional processes (Kuypers et al., 2019).

Microdosing psychedelic substances, most commonly LSD and psilocybin, has gained popularity in recent years due to their perceived benefits and effectiveness (Anderson et al., 2019; Kuypers et al., 2019; Lea et al., 2020). According to the 2021 Global Drug Survey, that collected data from 32000 participants across 22 countries, over 9% of respondents used LSD and psilocybin only in the context of microdosing, over 12% indulged in both recreational and microdoses and approximately 31% had also microdosed with other psychedelic substances, mostly MDMA, Ketamine and DMT (Winstock et al., 2021). By looking at trends such as growing online communities, e.g., Reddit forums, as well as popularity on mainstream and social media, it may be inferred that the practice of microdosing psychedelics has only grown since then.

Individuals mostly explore the practice of psychedelic microdosing on their own by customising dosage and frequencies that work best for them based on experiential knowledge and trial-and-error (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019) which may vary for everyone. However, the perceived benefits of psychedelics, including improved mental health, mood, sociability, and overall well-being, as well as alleviation of clinical symptoms (both psychological and physical, e.g., for mental health disorders and pain), improved cognitive function, creativity, focus, and energy, as well as a reduction of substance use, etc., are some frequent motivations behind microdosing (Breeksema et al., 2020; Anderson et al., 2019; Rootman et al., 2021).

Previous Literature on Psychedelic Microdosing

Microdosing had been described as one of the most under-explored areas of psychedelic research by Fadiman (2011), who, in his book, examined several aspects of psychedelic use, including diverse experiences and perspectives, familiarised audiences with the term and practice of microdosing psychedelics with the intent of enhancement of certain aspects of one's life, and hence is often referred to as a guide for people interested in microdosing (Kuypers et al., 2019). Since then, there has been a rapid growth in literature, specifically from 2018 onwards (Polito and Liknaitzky, 2022), including qualitative studies, clinical trials, controlled studies, commentaries, systematic reviews, meta-analysis, and so on (Anderson et al., 2019; Kuypers et al., 2019).

Polito and Liknaizky (2022) conducted one of the most comprehensive systematic reviews on microdosing psychedelics and examined 44 papers from 1955-2021. In particular, the review explored aspects of mental health, psychological functioning, clinical symptoms, wellbeing and attitudes, cognition and creativity, personality and sociability, conscious states, subjective awareness, pain perception, discomfort, neurobiology and physiology, and found evidence for both positive and negative effects. It complimented the findings of two earlier reviews conducted in 2020, however expanded its search to include prior studies that may be relevant and provide insightful information, e.g., explore the practice of microdosing before the legislative regulations were put in place. While Bornemann (2020) reviewed 21 studies from 2014–2019, Ona and Bouso (2020) reviewed 17 studies from 2018–2020, and both found positive effects, including improved mood and cognition, as well as negative effects, including discomfort and the exacerbation of psychiatric symptoms, as well as null effects.

Additionally, there has been substantial research to test microdosing psychedelics as a viable option to compliment or replace existing treatment methods and interventions for various mental health disorders. Another research reviewed 14 experimental studies with the goal of examining the phenomenon of establishing microdosing as a potential therapeutic approach in terms of usefulness, impact, and safety (Kuypers, 2020). While supporting the claims of its fellow reviews in terms of positive effects on symptom reduction and cognition, it found these pleasant experiences to be very subtle and short lived, accompanied with increased anxiety and cyclic patterns of depressive and euphoric mood for some microdosers. This highlights the variation and diversity of experiences individuals may face when microdosing psychedelic substances, which is a recurring theme found in most literature, e.g., Fadiman’s systematic exploration of the effects of microdoses, which included over 1000 participants and reported improved mood, energy, and overall health, but also increased headaches, PMS, and shingles; and Johansen et al.’s population study that reported no relation between psychedelics and mental health or suicidal ideation, questioning the idea of microdosing psychedelics as a plausible intervention for mental health (Breeksema et al., 2020; Fadiman and Korb, 2019; Anderson et al., 2019; Johansen and Krebs, 2015).

Nevertheless, studies suggest that people increasingly experiment with microdosing psychedelics for mental health as a form of self-managed therapy due to their perceived

positive effects, growing media awareness, ease of access, as well as disappointment with existing treatments and interventions (Lea et al., 2020; Rootman et al., 2021). Qualitative studies aimed at exploring psychedelic microdosing in terms of motivations, experiences, rationality, and effects serve as a basis to make more informed decisions, expand personal knowledge, evaluate the pros and cons as well as identify themes, trends, and patterns in this rapidly emerging field (Johnstad, 2018; Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019). However, this may also expose microdosers to higher risks, including negative legal consequences, danger of ingesting an impure or unknown substance, incorrect dosage or frequencies, etc., consequently discouraging them from indulging in the practice that they have found beneficial (Kuypers et al., 2019; Johnstad, 2018).

Considering the challenges stated above and the positive effects consistently highlighted in literature, it may be argued that more flexible and adaptive policies regarding psychedelics are needed in order for individuals to have access to regulated and safe drugs and are able to benefit from this novel phenomenon. Additionally, there is a need for more discourse and research, specifically studies looking at long-term effects, randomised control trials investigating placebo effects, and global population studies that may provide insight on diverse experiences of microdosers across populations and explore the potential therapeutic effects to establish if psychedelic microdosing may be a plausible and safe treatment for psychiatric disorders and enhancement of mental health (Kuypers, 2021; Hovmand et al., 2023; Polito and Stevenson, 2019).

Rationale, Research Question and Aims

Though the practice of microdosing psychedelics is mostly self-administered in private settings and is informed by subjective experiences, research and motivations, recently there has been a rise in interest regarding this phenomenon in the media, popular culture as well as scientific literature (Rootman et al., 2021). However, as it is a fairly novel idea and a stigma still exists to some extent regarding psychedelics, the amount of existing literature that looks at integrating psychedelic microdoses into daily lives to enhance certain aspects, is insufficient to critically explore this phenomenon. As most knowledge is through informal means, experimentation is self-administered and there is a growing public interest, it may be argued that the media oversimplifies the act of microdosing psychedelics and overhypes and overemphasises its

positive effects, with little to no regard given to the potential challenges or negative effects (Partridge et al., 2011).

There are a lot of things that remain unknown and hence, we were able to identify a gap that needed to be addressed. Despite efforts to qualitatively examine the perceived and felt effects of microdosing psychedelics on individuals, to our knowledge, there exists no such thematic synthesis that combines the findings from individual studies to provide a more comprehensive understanding of this phenomenon, particularly in regards to mental health. This research aims to contribute to the growing literature on microdosing psychedelics by exploring gaps, synthesizing findings of qualitative studies and addressing the effects of microdosing psychedelics on people's mental health. In doing so, we aim to look at trends and patterns, subjective understanding and perspectives, positive and negative effects, possible motivations and explanations for microdosing, felt experiences, as well as interrelationships between different aspects of microdosers' lives, e.g., productivity and how it relates to mental health, and hence, pave the way for future research.

Therefore, the research question being asked is:

How do people make sense of microdosing psychedelics in relation to mental health?

Methodology

We systematically searched five databases based on the research question and inclusion criteria derived using the Population-Interest-Context (PICO) framework, which aims to analyse human experience and social phenomena in qualitative research (Stern, Jordan and McArthur, 2014). Additionally, the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines and the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist were used to ensure the quality of studies being used and gain a visually representable and transparent search of all available and chosen literature for this thematic synthesis (CASP, 2018).

Selection Criteria

For this thematic synthesis, we selected papers that explored people's experiences with psychedelic microdosing and its relationship to certain aspects of their lives, including mental health and wellbeing. The eligibility criteria for the inclusion in the synthesis were qualitative, peer-reviewed studies in English language, presenting examinable findings, in both clinical & non-clinical settings, using human participants and focussing on microdosing psychedelics. Additionally, it was based on a modified PICO framework for qualitative reviews and employed a broad definition of psychedelics (see Table 1). This was done to ensure that the research was consistent with standards of conducting qualitative reviews and the criteria adequately identified the population, phenomenon of interest and context to gather a representative sample of papers to be screened and included in the synthesis to answer the research question (Stern, Jordan, and McArthur, 2014). The synthesis, however, excluded quantitative studies, studies published in other languages or in poor-quality journals, and outdated research. We also excluded reviews, book chapters, case-studies, commentaries, editorials, any grey literature, studies focusing on other drugs and cannabis, animal studies, inaccessible papers, and papers on databases that did not produce many results. This may have caused us to potentially miss out certain beneficial literature, however, this was done to streamline the process and establish a standardised method that could assure certain quality standards being upheld.

Table 1: PICO framework for this thematic synthesis

Population	Individuals who are involved in the microdosing of psychedelic substances (not for recreational purposes or as one-off instances)
Phenomenon of Interest	Experiences elicited or induced by deliberate microdosing of psychedelic substances, including classic and atypical psychedelics such as LSD, psilocybin, ibogaine, ayahuasca, kratom, ecstasy, MDMA, ketamine, DMT, peyote and DMA, but excluding cannabis, and how they may relate to mental health, function and overall wellbeing
Context	People in both clinical and non-clinical settings with experience of microdosing psychedelics, context that reflects mental health-related and other effects, through self-report data, both verbal and/or written as well as virtual and/or physical

Search Strategy

We carried out a systematic search in May 2023 for literature on “microdosing psychedelics”. Five databases with the most results were selected i.e., PubMed, PsycINFO, Web of Science, Scopus and Science Direct. The databases were searched extensively and systematically,

without time constraints, using a range of index and free-text terms in two categories. This was done to ensure that the papers obtained were representative and could potentially address the research question. The key index terms were “microdosing” or “micro-dosing” and “psychedelic” as they were the terms we were most interested in and were likely to produce the most relevant results. Two categories of free-text terms were used: 1) specific psychedelics, and 2) topics of potential interest. The first category consisted of various classic and atypical psychedelics including LSD, psilocybin, ibogaine, ayahuasca, kratom, ecstasy, MDMA, ketamine, DMT, peyote and DMA. The second category consisted of certain potential topics of interest including “mental”, “emotional” and “psychological” related results. All the five databases were searched using “OR-relations” within categories and “AND relations” between categories (see Table 2).

The preliminary systematic search of literature on the five selected databases identified 1806 results. A consolidated list was produced by compiling all search results and removing duplicates using a computer program (EndNote) as this reduced the chances for human error, making the process more reliable and rigorous. The final 680 papers were then divided amongst the authors and screened based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The papers were categorised into qualitative usable, qualitative potential and unusable (did not meet criteria or were inaccessible). Of these, 659 records were excluded based not meeting the inclusion criteria, e.g., were either quantitative, animal studies or commentaries etc. The selection process was conducted in accordance with the eligibility criteria as presented in the PRISMA flow diagram (see Figure 2) to attain a total of 21 papers then assessed in-depth using the CASP checklist (see Appendix 1). This ensured that only the highest quality of studies got selected as the checklist critically appraises each study based on ten distinct categories in a rigorous, systematic, and transparent manner (CASP, 2018), resulting in ten studies being used for this thematic synthesis.

Table 2: Search terms

(microdosing* OR micro-dosing*) AND (psychedelic* OR LSD OR psilocybin OR ayahuasca OR DMT OR ecstasy OR Ibogaine OR ketamine OR kratom OR peyote OR MDMA OR DMA)

(microdosing* OR micro-dosing*) AND (psychedelic* OR mental OR emotional OR psychological)

Figure 2: PRISMA flow diagram

Study Selection and Characteristics

All the selected studies (10) were published between 2018-2023 and included a wide variety of methods including semi-structured interviews (4), an online survey, analysis of Subreddits and other online forums (2) as well as YouTube videos and comments (3). This gave us qualitative data from 104 interviewees, 118 survey respondents, 328 threads (Reddit and a Danish online forum posts and comments) and 92 videos with over 55000 comments (YouTube). All the studies recruited participants through internet forums, social media, research platforms or online data. Where reported, most participants were male, aged between 17-69 years (average being late 20s-early 30s), white (though research was conducted in various cultural contexts, e.g., Danish, British, etc.), educated, middle or upper-middle class, and had varied psychedelic use experience (2 months-25 years). The most used psychedelics reported were LSD and psilocybin, either alone or in combination, and almost all participants reported improvements to certain aspects of their lives as motivations behind microdosing.

Analysis & Synthesis

Qualitative research aims to capture an in-depth and holistic view of the participants' perspectives and experiences. It is an interpretative approach that attempts to explain diverse phenomena in terms of people's meaning-making process (Ritchie et al., 2013). Qualitative researchers employ a variety of tools and methods focussing on the 'what', 'why' and 'how', rather than limiting responses to quantifiable data, allowing for the complexity and richness of data needed to address real-world scenarios. Hence, there is no one way of carrying out qualitative research and analysis as this may depend on several factors including ontology and epistemology, aims of the research, participant characteristics, and so on (Ritchie et al., 2013).

This study analyses the ten selected papers (details in search strategy) using a thematic synthesis, based on thematic analysis, which is a tried-and-tested method of analysis that integrates the papers' findings in a transparent, detailed, and rigorous manner to identify recurrent themes and heterogeneities (Thomas and Harden, 2008).

The thematic synthesis was based on a thematic analysis of each study, which is a flexible and rigorous method that provides an in-depth account of data while preserving its complexity, to

identify, analyse and report patterns or themes within studies (Braun and Clarke, 2006). We adopted an inductive and latent thematic analysis, a bottom-up technique that focusses on data-driven themes rather than fitting the data into pre-determined categories and is interpretative i.e., mindful of underlying ideas, notions, and presuppositions etc. (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This was done to ensure the depth and level of analysis required to adequately address the research question, value data subjectivity, and minimise biased decision-making, e.g., modifying data to fit pre-decided themes.

The six steps of thematic analysis were followed for each study, which was integrated into our thematic synthesis as it was conducted in various stages, was non-linear and was revised multiple times. The selected studies were read multiple times to understand and familiarize ourselves with the content and context of each study. The results sections of each study were converted into transcripts and thematically analysed. Each line was coded systematically to form primary codes, notes, observations, and reflections. Next, these initial primary codes were combined to form potential themes, were refined, defined, analysed, and recorded using tables. These themes were then re-analysed and compared across papers to develop new primary themes consistent with the different studies and tables were made for each theme to record data systematically (see Appendix 3). Heterogeneities were also documented and compared independently. The primary themes were then discussed amongst authors and categorised into descriptive themes based on their recurrence, interpretation, similarities and differences across studies, etc. While all the authors may have different labels for each theme, the underlying analysis largely remained similar, and categories were refined based on discussions. Finally, we clustered and refined the descriptive themes to generate analytical themes that captured the findings across the studies more coherently and holistically (Thomas and Harden, 2008; Breeksema et al., 2020).

Theoretical Orientation

Qualitative research is largely rooted within the philosophical debates of ontology (beliefs about the nature of the social world) and epistemology (nature of knowledge and how it can be acquired) (Ritchie et al., 2013). This impacts the research methodology and approach as well as how to interpret, understand and make sense of people's experiences and "reality" (Ritchie et al., 2013). This research adopts a critical realist (ontology) and interpretivist (epistemology)

approach to understanding how people make sense of microdosing psychedelics for mental health. Critical realism refers to the idea that reality is multi-layered. It consists of the empirical domain (what we can experience through our senses), actual domain (what exists regardless of us being able to observe or experience), and real domain (underlying mechanisms and processes) (Ritchie et al., 2013). This implies that reality is extremely complex, making our understanding of it fragmented and imperfect and thus, needing critical analysis and examination. This makes this approach the most appropriate for this research as it encourages critical evaluation and understanding contextual and subjective experiences of people microdosing psychedelics. Interpretivism usually goes hand-in-hand with critical realism as it shares the fundamental value of reality and experiences being complex and perspective-dependent (Ritchie et al., 2013). Interpretivism, being largely applied in qualitative research, emphasises and values the participants' and researchers' interpretation of their socially constructed world to know and understand certain phenomena (Ritchie et al., 2013). This approach is directly in-line with the research question as the study aims to understand how people make sense of their experiences with microdosing psychedelics and in doing so, aims to consider people's subjective experiences and interpretations while acknowledging and appreciating that reality can never be captured empirically, be completely value-free or be the same for everyone.

Reflexivity

Reflexivity encompasses a set of continuous, collaborative, and multifaceted practices by which researchers can self-consciously critique, appraise and evaluate the influence of their subjectivity and context on the research (Olmos-Vega et al., 2022). Due to the complexity of conducting qualitative research, reflexivity is essential to neutralise and acknowledge potential bias, respect, and value the researcher's subjectivity, and establish some extent of transparency and meaningfulness.

Prior to this research, I did not have any knowledge or personal experience of psychedelics, especially microdosing. I had been in proximity to situations where psychedelic substances had been consumed recreationally or as signs of deviance from the norm, and had the experience described to me. However, I had never been involved in the practice myself due to certain religious, cultural, and legal restrictions.

Nonetheless, the more I researched on the topic, the more I realised that psychedelics can be much more than that- they can be used in small amounts, be controlled, and useful. I think that throughout this research process, my view of psychedelics has shifted greatly, and I no longer see it as an object of deviant behaviour, rather a complex substance with a wide variety of applications, particularly microdosing as it's a novel phenomenon that may have potential application for therapeutic practices. As a someone passionate about mental health and holistic/alternative healing, I think microdosing psychedelics is ground-breaking, specifically considering the negative effects of psychoactive drugs and other medication. However, I do feel a little hesitant promoting its due to fear of forming addictions, overdosing, consuming the incorrect substance or unknown long-term effects.

Nevertheless, throughout this research, I have tried to acknowledge my bias, reflect on my subjective practices, and approach the topic with an open mind by adopting a tabula-rasa and critically evaluating the research process. I have been surprised by some of the findings of this research and my view has considerably shifted since project commenced. I am curious to explore more about the impacts of psychedelic use and the practicality and possibility of them being employed as a potential treatment or intervention for improving mental health and wellbeing. I am also interested in how these substances may be regulated by adopting changes in law and policies to ensure safer and decriminalised usage, in both clinical and non-clinical settings.

Results

The selected studies highlight several essential ideas in the context of microdosing psychedelics, which are presented thematically in this chapter to address how people make sense of microdosing for mental health (research question). The themes are categorised into perceived effects and observations, impacts on mental health, psychosocial and general wellbeing, and cognitive functioning. Each theme discusses both the positive and negative experiences reported by microdosers in diverse settings and situations and explores the extent of the effects and motivations behind the practice.

Making Sense of Microdosing Psychedelics: Perceived Effects

With the growing awareness and acceptance of psychedelic use, paired with an increase in academic literature and media hype, many individuals have started experimenting with psychedelics for non-recreational use (Polito and Stevenson, 2019). There is a general attitude shift regarding impacts and effects, especially when microdosing, resulting to individuals' having positive expectations and hence, noticing said effects or improvements. This raises the question of placebo effect and the role of individuals' expectations and beliefs:

“I just think that placebo must play a huge role in all this micro-dosing stuff...There's no medical evidence that taking LSD every day should cure anything. There's no research suggesting any benefits.” (Holm et al., 2023)

“I don't know if it was a placebo effect of genuinely the MD [microdosing] but I felt like a ninja...I would love to credit it all to microdosing but I'm sure it's also partly my own awareness...I don't think I would've reached it on my own, however” (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

Though there exists little scientific evidence suggesting testable links to improved mental health, microdosing psychedelics may contribute medically or by producing a placebo effect or motivation-response, e.g., just the belief that they may produce favourable results. Furthermore, from an individual's perspective, the concern that it may be a hoax and not

actually a medical phenomenon, may be secondary due to the experienced benefits (Fadiman and Korb, 2019).

Another common theme was that psychedelic microdosing was not a purely experimental or impulsive decision, rather it was rational, well-researched, and done with precaution and intent (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019; Ryan, Copello, and Fox, 2023). This may be observed in the comprehensive regimen followed (frequency, dosage, drug type, etc.) and how microdosers commented about their experiences (practicality, motives, incorporation into daily life, benefits, and challenges). Most microdosers in the studies considered the practise compatible with their daily life, with only a few reporting negative experiences, specifically at the start of their microdosing journeys:

“I was feeling very tired and had a martial arts class to attend for the first time...This was my second time microdosing shrooms, and I dosed...to peak well before the class and still just be stimulated and in a good positive mood for it. This backfired massively...I found it very hard to follow instructions and had a huge body load.”
(Johnstad, 2018)

This suggests that microdosing psychedelics may cause certain unwanted effects, e.g., loss of focus, physical difficulties, noticeable tripping etc. Thus, participants often microdosed for the first time on a day off to experience the effects, acquire confidence, and modify dosage based on their experience (Webb, Copes, and Hendricks, 2019).

Participants in the studies most commonly microdosed psilocybin and LSD, usually between 0.1-0.6 g and 4-25 mcg per dose, respectively, every three to four days (Johnstad, 2018; Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019; Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019). However, there was no consensus on which psychedelic was most effective and participants found some psychedelics worked better for their conditions than others and identified certain effects, e.g., stimulation levels, that influenced their decisions (Johnstad, 2018; Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022). Thus, preferences regarding when to microdose, what substance to use, what frequency or dosage, etc. varied for individuals based on personal experiences, situations, and motivations and was heavily influenced by research, experimentation, felt experiences, and trial-and-error:

“I dose 10 mcg LSD twice per week. I came to this amount by administering doses at 5 mcg intervals within the following range [5–25]. I have found that 10 mcg is the most beneficial. Any more and I’m a little too impressionable to distraction, any less and there’s no benefit.” (Johnstad, 2018)

“I was the rabbit in lab doing experiments on my brain...I started with psilocybin and then included LSD just to see the differences which were vivid at least to me.” (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

This shows how participants may self-experiment to develop their own regime rather than following pre-suggested ones like the Hoffman schedule (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023) to find their ‘sweet spot’ (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019). It also suggests a degree of responsibility in exploring the effects of psychedelics as dosage and individual responses can vary significantly.

Furthermore, most participants in the included studies aspired to improve specific aspects of their lives through microdosing. While motivations varied, some commonly experienced effects can be categorised into:

- a) improved mental health and reduced symptoms for disorders,
- b) better psychosocial and general wellbeing, and
- c) enhanced cognitive functioning for better mental health.

Other themes, such as concerns regarding risks, physiological effects and tolerance were also noticed in some papers. The three major themes largely overlap, making it difficult to attribute certain experiences and effects to a particular category, however, that is not the goal of this research. The anecdotal reports by participants in the ten selected studies help address the research question, “How people make sense of microdosing psychedelics for mental health?” by looking at perceived positive effects, motivations, and subjective experiences that link to different aspects of one’s life and, direct and indirect, impacts on mental health.

Mental Health

The most reported effect of microdosing psychedelics was a reduction in symptoms associated with depression and anxiety. Individuals living with depression and anxiety for long periods of

time and being disappointed with traditional pharmacological treatments had moved towards microdosing due to its lack of negative side-effects, positive and generally quicker results and more ‘natural’ or ‘holistic’ approach:

“Microdosing LSD has been the best thing that happened in my life. Dealing with serious depression for 35 years... it’s now GONE!” (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)

“I have had very positive results from infrequent psilocybin microdosing. I have found fast and relatively long-lasting relief from depression and social anxiety doing this, as compared to other pharmaceutical options I’ve been offered such as SSRIs [selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors], and without the intolerable (for me) side effects.” (Johnstad, 2018)

The extracts provide first-hand accounts of people who microdosed psychedelics to alleviate mental health conditions, such as long-standing depression and anxiety and improve well-being more effectively as compared to pharmacological treatments. Despite promising outcomes, these reports must be evaluated considering microdosing response variance and placebo effects. Hence, requiring further research before drawing any definitive conclusions on its therapeutic potential.

Moreover, microdosing was reported to improve mood, emotional regulation, stress, and response management. Microdosing not only helped them stay calm and positive but also manage their feelings, process them in a healthier and more effective way as well as build resilience:

“It’s [microdosing] like hacking your brain, you know? Like being a better you. ... I feel like you’re generally happier, more upbeat, kind of more open minded also.” (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)

“I decided to start microdosing again because I’ve been having trouble keeping my emotions under control (namely anger and frustration) and it has taken a noticeable toll not only on my work but also in my friendships” (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

This supports the idea that microdosing is a technique for ‘hacking’ the brain to become a better version of oneself. Consistent with anecdotal accounts of improved mood and emotional regulation, they expressed feeling happier, emotionally balanced and having fewer negative feelings. While these reports highlight potential benefits, it's important to consider that scientific study on microdosing remains a relatively underexplored area, and individual experiences highly vary.

Though, few reports indicating that microdosing psychedelics helped individuals manage symptoms of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), Asperger’s, Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), Bipolar and other mental health disorders were of great importance as it helps understand the impact and possibility for psychedelic microdosing to replace or supplement existing treatments and interventions:

“Instead of blunting our emotional response to trauma that we’ve had in the past, the trauma starts to come up, and we have to look at it and integrate it in a way that helps us to become a more healthy self.” (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)

“I had tremendous success in recently treating decades of aftermath of long term abuse, trauma and loss with full dose psychedelic medicines. I am microdosing now for maintenance in conjunction with talk therapy and it has been nothing short of miraculous for me.” (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

“I’m bipolar and used anti-depressives my entire life. The only medicine that works for me is Psilocybin mushrooms.. I have never felt better.” (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)

The excerpts emphasise on the therapeutic benefits and how psychedelics can help individuals cope with mental health disorders, long-term abuse, trauma, and loss, either alone or in combination with other treatments, such as talk therapy. The results imply microdosing may encourage emotional healing and growth through facing and processing trauma rather than subduing emotions or using pharmacological treatments, which may be less effective in the long run. These experiences suggest that psychedelics have promising therapeutic potential and may be empowering for individuals, however, each person's experience is unique, and more

research is required to determine the long-term efficacy and safety of such practices. It's also essential to make sure that these substances are utilised within the legal and ethical boundaries, and under the proper guidance or supervision to avoid negative consequences.

Thus, it is important to consider that microdosing may not be suitable for everyone, e.g., it may cause or exacerbate certain clinical symptoms, increase anxiety and induce feelings of discomfort, as reported in certain cases. Though these occurrences were mostly attributed to incorrect doses or the impact of negative internal states, and hence were rare, they may discourage individuals to continue the practice and cause more harm than good, making navigation complicated:

“I noticed that after a certain point, the benefits fade, and microdosing instead serves to exacerbate my mental health problems.” (Johnstad, 2018)

“Very very rarely if I get the type of physical anxiety [physical sensations of anxiety] it will feel worse than normal ...but those instances are very rare” (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

“I feel that microdosing has a lot to do with how you feel inside at the moment and/or what you wish to achieve at the moment. I feel that psychedelics amplify, in a way, our current feelings/needs/wants. SO if people are feeling depressed or anxious, I believe that they shouldn't do it if they don't know what they are getting into, because for some weak hearted, it might trigger something that will be beyond their control. Although overall I am definitely convinced of the therapeutic power of psychedelics...but I also know that some people cannot handle them.” (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

These reflect a range of perspectives and emphasise the importance of understanding individual responses, potential side effects, and the role of mindset and emotional states. The third report, specifically, suggests that psychedelics can amplify existing emotions and needs, hence, cautioning those struggling with negative feelings or mental health concerns, as they may trigger unpredictable responses. This also highlights that microdosing can have diminishing returns and may worsen mental health issues via exacerbation of clinical symptoms. Although rarely, suggesting it's not a one-size-fits-all solution. The complexity of microdosing

psychedelics is shown in these reports and need for careful consideration of various factors and risks are highlighted.

Psychosocial and General Wellbeing

As microdosing psychedelics reduces social anxiety and boosts mood, it allows for enhanced social functioning and interpersonal relationships as individuals are more socially active and able to get out of their ‘shell’, without overthinking, indulging in self-doubt or feeling over-conscious. Participants reported feeling more energetic, building intimate connections, and enjoying themselves a lot more than they did without microdosing:

“I would notice myself being more outgoing and just, I would hear myself talk and go like, ‘Wow! I wouldn’t normally have said something like that!’” (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)

“I have gained so much confidence it's crazy. I have a new career lined up. I am sociable, I am happy to speak up for myself. I don't even recognise the person that I was!... No social anxiety...For the first time ever” (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

The excerpts provide insight on how microdosing helped overcome personal barriers and social anxiety, raise self-confidence and pro-social habits, and improve career and sociability. The drastic transformation, personal development, newfound assertiveness, self-expression, and energy may help microdosers break cycles of negative thoughts and patterns and build meaningful relationships, improving mental and emotional health. Additionally, empathy from interpersonal interactions may be extended to oneself contributing positively self-acceptance and improved mental health.

Improved mindfulness and self-insight was another recurrent theme as microdosing psychedelics helped participants connect better with themselves, develop empathy, groundedness, being ‘present’ and reflect on themselves as well as the world around them to adopt behaviours and outlooks consistent with their goals:

“Since dosing I’ve become more in-touch with what I feel and as a result that helps me make decisions about getting to where I want to be” (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

“I believe the greatest thing I learnt from microdosing was to stop trying to solve problems I perceived about myself and just accept them for what they were. Accept myself for who I am, relax, stop overthinking everything because at the end of the day none of this matters so you may as well enjoy yourself however you see fit.” (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

This shows how microdosing can improve emotional well-being by inducing a shift in cognitive states and schemas about oneself and situations. It enhances self-awareness, emotional connectedness, mindfulness, and emotional intelligence, which subsequently improve decision making and goal-oriented behaviours. The shift from self-criticism to self-acceptance is essential as it may reduce negative thoughts and emotions, improving mental health and fostering empowerment and resilience. However, these reports may be subjective and not representative of everyone's experiences as certain disadvantages and negative experiences were also reported including increased social anxiety, being ‘extra chatty’, ‘too loud’ or ‘exuberant’ in interactions and feeling depersonalised after microdosing.

Another aspect impacted positively by microdosing psychedelics is a reduction in unhealthy habits and consumption of substances such as alcohol, cigarettes, cannabis, caffeine etc., as well as adopting healthier lifestyles and enhancement of sensory perception:

“I’m trying to quit smoking using a vape, I’ve quit cannabis abuse and I use a fraction of amphetamine than I used before. Increased interest in many things (hiking, music, traveling)...” (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

“Normally, I drink a lot of alcohol to cope with the heavy stress/workload...I had zero desire to be intoxicated because I knew it would interfere with the very clear benefit I was receiving from microdosing...Promoted healthier habits..” (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

“It’s more of a small perceptual enhancement of all you do...” (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

These excerpts suggest microdosers may be more likely to be able to give up certain addictions due to reduced urges and impulses and improved energy, mood, and quality of life. This not only helped them quit unhealthy or unwanted habits but also adopt healthier ones, e.g., meditation, eating healthier, exercising etc., which indirectly improved their mental health and wellbeing. It also led to enhanced senses and more fulfilling experiences which may contribute positively to mental health.

However, due to heightened senses, individuals may feel negative emotions and experiences more strongly as well. Psychedelic consumption was also associated with overstimulation, which caused microdosers to become hyper, unable to sleep, ‘sloppy’, and experience negative emotions:

“The only disadvantage I’ve had is there is no off switch as such on the mushrooms...I may feel my brains more active...and I can’t sleep because I’m thinking away more than usual” (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

“Another is that your mind gets too far open and you start to become so sad when thinking about the state of the world and all the suffering everywhere” (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

Thus, microdosers may experience exaggerated negative emotions and thoughts, e.g., insecurity, sadness, overthinking etc. This may accentuate anxiety and hence, have negative impacts on mental health. However, as the number of accounts highlighting this concern are few, it may be considered that perhaps there may be other factors contributing to these experiences, e.g., incorrect dosage, substance, settings, or internal states etc.

Cognitive Functioning

Poor mental health often manifests itself in the inability to do daily tasks such as procrastination, lack of motivation and organisation, poor performance and so on. Psychedelic

microdosing is reported to positively impact one's cognitive functioning by lifting a 'mental fog' and enhancing focus, creativity, and performance, both professionally and academically:

"It's just more like you're on your game. ... You're just 100% with it, got it going on, you know? You actually kind of walk around like you're the Wolf of Wall Street, like you got a one up on everybody." (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)

"It's like a psychedelic cup of coffee ... sharpens your focus and intuition, increases productivity and energy and also one's ability to think outside the box. Thoughts and ideas come effortlessly" (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

Thus, microdosing may enhance cognitive functioning for better mental health via improving creativity, adaptability, confidence, energy, and so on. Furthermore, doing well professionally or academically may also improve one's sense of self, esteem, mood and impact general wellbeing.

However, due to the overstimulation sometimes experienced by microdosers, they may experience negative impacts and diminished focus or motivation etc., contributing to opposing reports and enabling a cycle of negative experiences and emotions in the long run which would impact one's mental health as well:

"I am a grad student who works in a lab, and have md'd [author's note: "md" means microdosed/microdosing] on days where I was doing rote tasks. I found md to make these tasks a little more enjoyable, likely due to my overall mood increase. One day while I was md, something unexpected happened that required more critical thinking and dexterity than a typical lab day. I found that things were amplified now in a more negative way—I was more stressed about the event, and more anxious about making mistakes." (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

This shows that microdosing can improve performance by making otherwise mundane tasks enjoyable, alternatively, it may backfire sometimes and result in increased anxiety and stress. This highlights the complexity of microdosing psychedelics and suggests that it may not be universally beneficial and so, caution may be practiced, specifically with regards to individual differences, task specificity, setting, type and dosage, etc.

Nevertheless, microdosing psychedelics is largely reported to have positive effects on individuals with improved mental health in relation to disorders and emotional regulation, especially depression and anxiety, enhanced psychosocial and general wellbeing as well as cognitive functioning for improved mental health, with few reports of negative experiences. These help us understand the motivations behind the practice and how people make sense of navigating with microdosing psychedelics. However, there are certain concerns expressed by participants that are valid and need to be considered, such as risks and challenges faced by microdosers, specifically around legality and safety of substances, uncertainty with regards to long-term effects, variation in subjective experiences and so on. These may cause anxiety and evoke negative or mixed emotions in microdosers as well as hinder the argument for the wider application of microdosing for mental health and increase stigma:

“Honestly I must admit that it is a bit unnerving to be on the forefront of microdose experimentation...” (Johnstad, 2018)

“There is a risk, the risk is that we don’t know, there are a few rare reports of developing HPPD [Hallucinogen Persisting Perception Disorder], that’s about it. Any other potential problems, we simply don’t know about yet.” (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

“In general, I think that if you need a “security blanket” in the form of substances to cope with your life, then you need to change something more fundamentally.” (Holm et al., 2023)

The excerpts present a range of concerns expressed by microdosers, specifically considering the underexplored nature of psychedelic research and its complex legal status. Psychedelic substances are largely banned in most countries and consumption is highly stigmatised, exposing microdosers to risks and negative experiences, diminishing mental health. Furthermore, microdosing psychedelics may not be a ‘cure’ or ‘treatment’ in itself, rather a tool to assist better mental health, combined with several other factors including self-consciousness and motivation, development of healthier habits and coping mechanisms, conjunction with traditional interventions such as talk-therapy, mindfulness, etc.

In conclusion, all the anecdotal accounts mentioned in this chapter as well as in Appendix 3 provide an in-depth understanding and helps address how people make sense of microdosing psychedelics for mental health (research question). They highlight on the varied and subjective experiences of diverse groups of individuals and their meaning-making processes, thus, informing certain themes and guiding the findings for this thematic synthesis.

Discussion

This chapter discusses some of the key findings of the research while relating to previous psychedelic literature, evaluates the research in terms of both its strengths and limitations, highlights a few recommendations for future research and gaps to be addressed, followed by a conclusion for the research.

Findings

This thematic synthesis discovered several essential elements regarding how people made sense of microdosing psychedelics in relation to mental health (research question). This could be understood by exploring the motivations, perceived effects and felt experiences that contributed positively to individuals' mental health e.g., reduction in anxiety, depression, and clinical symptoms etc.

The motivations behind microdosing appeared to be similar across all studies i.e., participants wished to improve mental health, general and psychosocial wellbeing, and cognitive functioning (which linked to better mental health). This emphasizes microdosers' rationality and conscious, result-oriented, decision making as they developed a microdosing regime that worked best for them based on personal experimentation and extensive research to experience profound results, with exception of a few reported negative effects.

Most participants reported overlapping effects, such as improved mood in relation to all the three main themes i.e., mental health, psychosocial and general wellbeing, and cognitive functioning for better mental health.

Consistent with previous literature, the most reported effects were improved anxiety and depression, reduced symptoms for disorders such as PTSD, ADHD, and Bipolar etc., increased prosocial behaviour, and enhanced overall wellbeing via emotional regulation, and self-perception etc. (Breeksema et al., 2020; Kuypers et al., 2019; Gregorio et al., 2021). This supports the findings of earlier studies including clinical trials, meta-analysis and systematic

reviews and hence, provides relevant and congruous insights about felt experiences and effects of microdosing psychedelics and how it impacts mental health.

Moreover, most findings were interrelated and may have facilitated each other e.g., the reduction of clinical symptoms may be attributed to improvements in emotional processing, promotion of positive mood, mindfulness, self-acceptance, enhanced cognitive functioning, and so on. Multiple factors may be considered when trying to explain or infer these findings. For example, psychedelic microdosing may enhance emotional processing, regulation, and self-awareness, allowing individuals identify, understand and work through their emotions and underlying issues that may evoke anxiety, e.g., processing trauma by confrontation rather than avoidance, leading to symptom reduction, healthier coping mechanisms, and improved mental health via self-acceptance and empowerment. Psychedelics often induce a state of mindfulness and being present in the moment (Johnstad, 2018; Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019), leading to positive effects on symptoms by helping microdosers stay grounded, manage thoughts and emotions, practice gratitude, improve self-perception, and empathy for oneself, which may be extended to the outside world. Another possible explanation could be promotion of neuroplasticity and serotonin regulation induced by psychedelics (Artin, Zisook and Ramanathan, 2021). This may help microdosers adapt, rewire associations, and negative thought patterns, as well as improve emotional balance, stability, and mood to reduce anxiety and clinical symptoms. Enhanced cognitive functioning may also contribute to or be a sign of good mental health, e.g., increased motivation, creativity, and performance etc. It is also important to consider that while many of the effects overlap, many work together to produce therapeutic effects and improved mental health, e.g., enhanced performance may lead to better self-confidence and mood, which may reduce anxiety.

Another key finding was the effectiveness of psychedelic microdosing in reducing symptoms specifically for treatment-resistant and long-standing clinical disorders, including depression and anxiety. Some microdosers had started experimenting with microdosing as a last resort following disappointed with traditional interventions and treatments, highlighting their efficiency in achieving desired outcomes.

Although microdosing psychedelics for mental health had mostly positive effects, a few negative effects were also discussed in studies such as exacerbation of clinical symptoms,

increased anxiety, stress, discomfort, and negative thoughts and emotions such as insecurity, social anxiety, sadness, etc. The extent of this was unexpected as it remained underexplored in previously reviewed literature. In their review, Kuypers (2020) discovered the effects of microdosing psychedelics to be short-lived and subtle, highlighting another crucial aspect that may be further researched. Therefore, it is essential to consider that responses to psychedelic microdosing are highly variable and differ across individuals, settings, typology and dosage of the psychedelic as well as several other factors that might interact and impact one's experience. Furthermore, the added risks associated with psychedelic microdosing, such as long-term effects, illegality, and social stigma, may also cause participants distress and make navigation complex.

Moreover, as microdosers may have high expectations for symptom reduction and improved wellbeing, placebo effects may potentially affect results. This might lead to them experiencing exaggerated benefits and effects, consequently reducing anxiety and clinical symptoms as a placebo and highlighting the power of belief and positivity. The previous literature reviewed did not discuss the role of placebo in detail, however, a comprehensive review by Ona and Bouso (2020) examined 17 studies on placebo effect and found a positive association between reported effects and psychedelic ideologies. This finding may be extremely beneficial as it may be applied and integrated into existing therapeutic practices, such as positive psychology and other interventions to provide effective results.

However, as this research focuses solely on subjective experiences from ten qualitative papers, further research is required to explore the new avenues opened in psychedelic research, such as the feasibility of integrating psychedelic microdosing as a potential treatment for mental health, rather than as a self-managed form of therapy, either alone or in combination with existing therapeutic practices, as well as inquiring if it may be managed and maintained in the long-term without considerable negative effects.

Evaluation

This research is the first to conduct a thematic synthesis of qualitative literature exploring the motivations and impacts of microdosing psychedelics, systematically and rigorously, using

data from diverse settings and populations, to address how people make sense of this practice in relation to mental health.

All the studies included in this research were published in the last five years, as microdosing is a novel phenomenon, making the research relevant to current trends. This makes the findings useful in terms of application and generalisability, specifically as they can be used to infer if microdosing psychedelics may be used as a potential treatment for mental health conditions and enhancement of wellbeing. This also indicates the recent rise in interest and development of psychedelic research, which had been halted due to issues around legality and stigma (Kuypers et al., 2019; Smith, 2019; Fadiman, 2011). However, due to this 40+ year hiatus in psychedelic research and the phenomenon of microdosing being fairly recent, there were limited studies we could draw upon and comparisons were difficult due to a lack of academic acknowledgement (Fadiman, 2011), e.g., the impact of microdosing psychedelics vs. a specific intervention.

As the research uses in-depth qualitative data and is conducted systematically, explicitly explained in the methodology, it gives detailed information about microdosers' personal experiences and contexts and may be replicated by other researchers to ensure validity and reliability of findings. All the studies were taken from peer-reviewed databases and screened to assess the quality of studies being selected, e.g., via the CASP criteria, increasing research rigour.

The anecdotal reports by microdosers serve an essential element in fulfilling the research aim as they provide subjective explanations, motivations, and effects, both positive and negative, to understand the impact of psychedelic microdosing on reduction of clinical symptoms, improvement of psychosocial wellbeing, and enhanced cognitive functioning for better mental health outcomes. However, as the research focus was qualitative and on mental health, this limited the search quite considerably due to most of the recent psychedelic research, specifically on microdosing, being quantitative and in the form of small clinical trials (Polito and Liknaitzky, 2022).

Furthermore, we used a broad definition of 'psychedelics' and 'microdosing', including both classic and atypical psychedelic substances as well as different dosages, as long as the

perceived effect was within range and did not cause major alterations to conscious states (Breeksema et al., 2020). This was done to ensure that the research captured the impacts of psychedelic microdosing on mental health holistically, take into account diverse experiences and perspectives, and allow for comparisons across substances and practices to not miss any valuable information, e.g., microdosers reporting higher risks associated with Kratom as compared to LSD and Psilocybin (Prevete et al., 2021), negative experiences due to higher dosages (Holm et al., 2023), using microdosing as a stand-alone alternative to treatment vs in combination to therapy and medication (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022), etc.

However, due to lack of certain resources, accessibility issues, and time constraints, not all variations of the search terms could be explored, nor could some databases and studies be utilised, limiting the data on which findings are based. Nonetheless, as the selected studies varied in terms of data collection, e.g., via interviews, surveys, YouTube and Subreddit analysis etc., we may deduce that they allowed for a comprehensive analysis of the existing literature with high internal validity due to consistent findings.

Moreover, as the studies were not controlled trials and depended on self-reports, there may have been variations, e.g., how the experiences were expressed and interpreted, different aspects of the microdosers lives, such as usage of other drugs and practices, levels of depression and anxiety, length of microdosing experience, and many more confounding variables that could have impacted the studies and made objectivity difficult. Additionally, all the studies recruited participants online, leading to the self-selection of individuals with pro-microdosing views, higher education, and incomes etc. and hence, may have impacted representativeness and potentially skewed findings (Johnstad, 2018).

Additionally, it could also be noted that there existed a gender- and cultural-bias as most of the studies were Eurocentric and included predominantly male participants. Thrul and Garcia-Romeu (2021) highlight this racial-ethnic divide in psychedelic research as there is a severe underrepresentation of Black, Indigenous, and People of Colour, sexual and gender minority groups as well as those from developing countries making current research ‘white-washed’.

Nevertheless, as all the studies had a large number of participants, ensured anonymity, and provided in-depth details, we were able to infer some valuable findings from diverse groups of

participants, which would not have been possible for any one study to do. The reports varied from people microdosing for as early as 2 months to as long as 25 years and from ages ranging from 17 to 69 years, giving us a wide range of subjective experiences to draw on and adequately address the research question of how people make sense of microdosing psychedelics for mental health.

Suggestions for Future Research

This research aimed to address how people make sense of microdosing for mental health by exploring the motivations and effects experienced by microdosers via thematically synthesising qualitative research. Being first of its kind, the research explored some key findings, however, there remains a gap in literature regarding certain aspects of psychedelic microdosing and its impacts e.g., long-term effects, variations in settings, sustainability of symptom reduction, safety and effectiveness of the practice etc., highlighting the need for future research.

Psychedelic research has increased considerably over the past few years, coupled with an increase in microdosers reported i.e., over 9% of the respondents of the Global Drug Survey (2019). Existing literature establishes a strong argument for mental health benefits of microdosing, which may be more effective, holistic and have fewer side effects than traditional treatments and interventions, and thus, more than half of the microdosers are likely to completely stop taking medications after starting microdosing (Polito and Liknaitzky, 2022). This highlights how microdosers may explore psychedelics as a self-managed form of therapy via experimentation and research and prefer it to existing methods. However, due to microdosing being a personal, trial-and-error process (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019), there are not many scientific studies that encompass diverse groups of individuals and represent populations to adequately address this complex and novel phenomenon. Moreover, it may be argued that some studies have self-selecting participants which may sometimes be the same e.g., sub-reddit users in content analyses. Additionally, there is a gap in literature and comparisons between microdosing as a therapeutic practice and other treatments is extremely under-researched.

Due to the perceived and felt experiences reported in exiting studies, future researchers should explore the feasibility and sustainability of using microdosing to achieve therapeutic benefits

as there exists a heterogeneity in reports, i.e., both positive and negative effects are reported, and the application of psychedelic microdosing in conjunction with traditional treatments or on their own under-explored. Research suggests psychedelics may be used in therapeutic or medical practice to supplement treatment (Breeksema, 2020), however with careful consideration and it may be useful to co-produce treatment plans with professionals for safe and effective practice.

It may also be beneficial to research into whether psychedelic microdosing has clinical benefits or mental health and wellbeing enhancements beyond placebo effect (Polito and Liknaitzky, 2022) as that was an intriguing aspect identified in this research but not explored further due to methodological constraints. Placebo-controlled clinical studies and randomised control trials may be beneficial in exploring this empirically and establishing the case for using microdosing psychedelics as a treatment for mental health disorders and enhanced wellbeing.

Additionally, more in-field research, such as inpatient settings, may also be done to explore inter-relationships between microdosing psychedelics and various factors, as this research found strong correlations between mental health, psychosocial wellbeing, and cognitive functioning. However other factors such as settings, dosage and type of drugs, and internal emotional states etc., were observed but not analysed in-depth to keep the research focused on certain aspects to address the research question. Exploratory research into these may be valuable to account for the research-methodology bias (a lot of systematic reviews and quantitative research etc. is available but other types of methods and analysis e.g., observational studies, thematic synthesis, IPA etc. are not) and white-washing currently present in psychedelic research.

Another very unresearched area in psychedelics are long-term effects and risks of microdosing. As this is a novel phenomenon, some microdosers reported being unaware of anyone who had microdosed long-term and so, there is uncertainty regarding any future side-effects or safety concerns, such as dependence, condition/disorder e.g., Hallucinogen Persisting Perception Disorder (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019), or heart disease and obesity etc. This emphasises the need for longitudinal studies and more research on long-time microdosers to explore any persistent negative effects and if microdosing for mental health may be a sustainable and safe therapeutic practice. This may also help establish the case for potentially legalising certain

psychedelics for clinical practice, addressing stigma, and enabling inter-disciplinary research and discourse, such as with sociology and public policy etc., leading to further development of psychedelic research.

Conclusion

The research aimed to explore how people made sense of microdosing psychedelics in relation to mental health (research question). This was done by thematically synthesising the perceived and felt effects reported in the ten selected qualitative studies. The current research had identified and aimed to fill the gap in current psychedelic research as there was no such thematic synthesis present that addressed the research question and brought together various themes present in individual studies.

The findings suggested improvements in mental health with regards to reduced anxiety, depression, and clinical symptoms, increased psychosocial and general wellbeing and enhanced cognitive functioning for better mental health. The findings were consistent with the reviewed literature, with exception of a few unexpected findings and new observations such as the role of placebo, effect overlaps and variation of individual experiences.

The research was conducted using up-to-date and high-quality studies, however, there was a visible gender-, cultural- and sampling-bias observed. Moreover, the research conducted wasn't as thorough owing to time and resource constraints e.g., inaccessibility to certain databases and lack of many qualitative studies specifically on microdosing. Nonetheless, due to the high internal reliability between and within studies as well as age- and experience-diversity, the research may be considered valid and applicable to wider populations. Additionally, this research provides a comprehensive and systematic view of the methods and approaches used, which may be useful in informing future studies.

Lastly, recommendations for future research were made and gaps were identified that may be considered such as exploring the sustainability and safety of using psychedelic microdosing as a possible treatment for mental health disorders and improved wellbeing, feasibility of integrating them into therapeutic practice, long-term effects, and risks. These may be useful to

research as they would not only contribute to the growing literature on psychedelics but also help inform practices and future policies to benefit individuals and their mental health.

References

- Andersen, K.A.A., Carhart-Harris, R., Nutt, D.J. and Erritzoe, D. (2020). Therapeutic effects of classic serotonergic psychedelics: A systematic review of modern-era clinical studies. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 143(2). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/acps.13249>
- Anderson, T., Petranker, R., Christopher, A., Rosenbaum, D., Weissman, C., Dinh-Williams, L.-A., Hui, K. and Hapke, E. (2019). Psychedelic microdosing benefits and challenges: an empirical codebook. *Harm Reduction Journal*, [online] 16(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12954-019-0308-4>
- Andersson, M. and Kjellgren, A. (2019). Twenty percent better with 20 micrograms? A qualitative study of psychedelic microdosing self-rapports and discussions on YouTube. *Harm Reduction Journal*, 16(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12954-019-0333-3>
- Artin, H., Zisook, S. and Ramanathan, D. (2021). How do serotonergic psychedelics treat depression: The potential role of neuroplasticity. *World Journal of Psychiatry*, 11(6), pp.201–214. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5498/wjp.v11.i6.201>
- Askew, R. and Williams, L. (2021). Rethinking enhancement substance use: A critical discourse studies approach. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, p.102994. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2020.102994>
- Bornemann, J. (2020). The Viability of Microdosing Psychedelics as a Strategy to Enhance Cognition and Well-being - An Early Review. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 52(4), pp.300–308. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2020.1761573>
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006). Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, [online] 3(2), pp.77–101. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1191/1478088706QP063OA>
- Breeksema, J.J., Niemeijer, A.R., Krediet, E., Vermetten, E. and Schoevers, R.A. (2020). Psychedelic Treatments for Psychiatric Disorders: A Systematic Review and Thematic Synthesis of Patient Experiences in Qualitative Studies. *CNS Drugs*, 34(9), pp.925–946. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40263-020-00748-y>

Carhart-Harris, R.L. and Goodwin, G.M. (2017). The Therapeutic Potential of Psychedelic Drugs: Past, Present, and Future. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, [online] 42(11), pp.2105–2113. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2017.84>

Carhart-Harris, R.L., Bolstridge, M., Rucker, J., Day, C.M.J., Erritzoe, D., Kaelen, M., Bloomfield, M., Rickard, J.A., Forbes, B., Feilding, A., Taylor, D., Pilling, S., Curran, V.H. and Nutt, D.J. (2016). Psilocybin with Psychological Support for treatment-resistant depression: an open-label Feasibility Study. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, [online] 3(7), pp.619–627. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(16\)30065-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(16)30065-7)

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2018). CASP (Qualitative) Checklist. [online] Available at: https://casp-uk.net/images/checklist/documents/CASP-Qualitative-Studies-Checklist/CASP-Qualitative-Checklist-2018_fillable_form.pdf

Doblin, R.E., Christiansen, M., Jerome, L. and Burge, B. (2019). The Past and Future of Psychedelic Science: An Introduction to This Issue. *Journal of psychoactive drugs*, [online] 51(2), pp.93–97. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2019.1606472>

Fadiman, J. (2011). *The psychedelic explorer's guide : safe, therapeutic, and sacred journeys*. Rochester, Vt.: Park Street Press

Fadiman, J. and Korb, S. (2019). Might Microdosing Psychedelics Be Safe and Beneficial? An Initial Exploration. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 51(2), pp.118–122. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2019.1593561>

Gasser, P., Holstein, D., Michel, Y., Doblin, R., Yazar-Klosinski, B., Passie, T. and Brenneisen, R. (2014). Safety and Efficacy of Lysergic Acid Diethylamide-Assisted Psychotherapy for Anxiety Associated With Life-threatening Diseases. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, [online] 202(7), pp.513–520. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1097/nmd.0000000000000113>

Gregorio, D.D., Aguilar-Valles, A., Preller, K.H., Heifets, B.D., Hibicke, M., Mitchell, J. and Gobbi, G. (2021). Hallucinogens in Mental Health: Preclinical and Clinical Studies on LSD, Psilocybin, MDMA, and Ketamine. *Journal of Neuroscience*, [online] 41(5), pp.891–900. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1659-20.2020>

Griffiths, R.R., Johnson, M.W., Carducci, M.A., Umbricht, A., Richards, W.A., Richards, B.D., Cosimano, M.P. and Klinedinst, M.A. (2016). Psilocybin produces substantial and sustained decreases in depression and anxiety in patients with life-threatening cancer: A randomized double-blind trial. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, [online] 30(12), pp.1181–1197. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881116675513>

Hofmann, A. (1970). *The Discovery of LSD and Subsequent Investigations on Naturally Occuring Hallucinogens*.

Holm, S., Petersen, M.A., Enghoff, O. and Hesse, M. (2023). Psychedelic discourses: A qualitative study of discussions in a Danish online forum. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, [online] 112, p.103945. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2022.103945>

Hovmand, O.R., Poulsen, E.D., Arnfred, S. and Storebø, O.J. (2023). Risk of bias in randomized clinical trials on psychedelic medicine: A systematic review. *Journal of Psychopharmacology (Oxford, England)*, [online] 37(7), pp.649–659. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/02698811231180276>

Hupli, A., Berning, M., Zhuparris, A. and Fadiman, J. (2019). Descriptive assemblage of psychedelic microdosing: Netnographic study of Youtube™ videos and on-going research projects. *Performance Enhancement & Health*, 6(3-4), pp.129–138. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peh.2019.01.001>

Johansen, P.-Ø. and Krebs, T.S. (2015). Psychedelics not linked to mental health problems or suicidal behavior: A population study. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 29(3), pp.270–279. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881114568039>

Johnstad, P.G. (2018). Powerful substances in tiny amounts. *Nordic Studies on Alcohol and Drugs*, [online] 35(1), pp.39–51. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1455072517753339>

Kuypers, K.P., Ng, L., Erritzoe, D., Knudsen, G.M., Nichols, C.D., Nichols, D.E., Pani, L., Soula, A. and Nutt, D. (2019). Microdosing psychedelics: More questions than answers? An overview and suggestions for future research. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, [online] 33(9), pp.1039–1057. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881119857204>

Kuypers, K.P.C. (2020). The therapeutic potential of microdosing psychedelics in depression. *Therapeutic Advances in Psychopharmacology*, 10, p.204512532095056. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/2045125320950567>

Kuypers, K.P.C. (2021). Microdosing Psychedelics as a Promising New Pharmacotherapeutic. *Modern CNS Drug Discovery*, pp.257–274. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62351-7_18

Lea, T., Amada, N. and Jungaberle, H. (2019). Psychedelic Microdosing: A Subreddit Analysis. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 52(2), pp.1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2019.1683260>

Lea, T., Amada, N., Jungaberle, H., Shecke, H. and Klein, M. (2020). Microdosing psychedelics: Motivations, subjective effects and harm reduction. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 75, p.102600. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2019.11.008>

Luoma, J.B., Chwyl, C., Bathje, G.J., Davis, A.K. and Lancelotta, R. (2020). A Meta-Analysis of Placebo-Controlled Trials of Psychedelic-Assisted Therapy. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, [online] 52(4), pp.1–11. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2020.1769878>

Moreno, F.A., Wiegand, C.B., Taitano, E.K. and Delgado, P.L. (2006). Safety, Tolerability, and Efficacy of Psilocybin in 9 Patients With Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, [online] 67(11). Available at: <https://www.psychiatrist.com/jcp/ocd/safety-tolerability-efficacy-psilocybin-patients-obsessive/>

Olmos-Vega, F.M., Stalmeijer, R.E., Varpio, L. and Kahlke, R. (2022). A practical guide to reflexivity in qualitative research: AMEE Guide No. 149. *Medical Teacher*, [online] 45(149), pp.1–11. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159x.2022.2057287>

Ona, G. and Bouso, J.C. (2020). Potential safety, benefits, and influence of the placebo effect in microdosing psychedelic drugs: A systematic review. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 119. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2020.09.035>

Partridge, B.J., Bell, S.K., Lucke, J.C., Yeates, S. and Hall, W.D. (2011). Smart Drugs ‘As Common As Coffee’: Media Hype about Neuroenhancement. *PLoS ONE*, 6(11), p.e28416. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0028416>

Petranker, R., Kim, J. and Anderson, T. (2022). Microdosing as a Response to the Meaning Crisis: A Qualitative Analysis. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, p.002216782210750. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/00221678221075076>

Polito, V. and Liknaitzky, P. (2022). The emerging science of microdosing: A systematic review of research on low dose psychedelics (1955 – 2021) and recommendations for the field. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 139, p.104706. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2022.104706>

Polito, V. and Stevenson, R.J. (2019). A systematic study of microdosing psychedelics. *PLOS ONE*, [online] 14(2), p.e0211023. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211023>

Prevete, E., Hupli, A., Marrinan, S., Singh, D., Udine, B.D., Bersani, G., Kuypers, K.P.C., Ramaekers, J.G. and Corazza, O. (2021). Exploring the use of Kratom (*Mitragyna speciosa*) via the YouTube data tool: A novel netnographic analysis. *Emerging Trends in Drugs, Addictions, and Health*, 1, p.100007. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etched.2021.100007>

Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Nicholas, C.M. and Ormston, R. (2013). *Qualitative Research Practice: a Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*. 2nd ed. Los Angeles: Sage

Rootman, J.M., Kryskow, P., Harvey, K., Stamets, P., Santos-Brault, E., Kuypers, K.P.C., Polito, V., Bourzat, F. and Walsh, Z. (2021). Adults who microdose psychedelics report health related motivations and lower levels of anxiety and depression compared to non-microdosers. *Scientific Reports*, [online] 11(1), p.22479. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-01811-4>

Rucker, J.J.H., Iliff, J. and Nutt, D.J. (2018). Psychiatry & the psychedelic drugs. Past, present & future. *Neuropharmacology*, [online] 142, pp.200–218. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2017.12.040>

Ryan, R.S., Copello, A. and Fox, A.P. (2023). Experiences of microdosing psychedelics in an attempt to support wellbeing and mental health. *BMC Psychiatry*, 23(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-023-04628-9>

Sanches, R.F., de Lima Osório, F., dos Santos, R.G., Macedo, L.R.H., Maia-de-Oliveira, J.P., Wichert-Ana, L., de Araujo, D.B., Riba, J., Crippa, J.A.S. and Hallak,

J.E.C. (2016). Antidepressant Effects of a Single Dose of Ayahuasca in Patients With Recurrent Depression. *Journal of Clinical Psychopharmacology*, 36(1), pp.77–81. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1097/jcp.0000000000000436>

Smith, D.E. (2019). The Role of the Journal of Psychedelic Drugs in the Evolution of Psychedelic Medicine. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 51(2), pp.98–101. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.2019.1589607>

Stern, C., Jordan, Z. and McArthur, A. (2014). Developing the Review Question and Inclusion Criteria. *AJN, American Journal of Nursing*, 114(4), pp.53–56. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.naj.0000445689.67800.86>

Thomas, J. and Harden, A. (2008). Methods for the thematic synthesis of qualitative research in systematic reviews. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, [online] 8(1), pp.1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-8-45>

Thrul, J. and Garcia-Romeu, A. (2021). Whitewashing psychedelics: racial equity in the emerging field of psychedelic-assisted mental health research and treatment. *Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy*, 28(3), pp.211–214. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09687637.2021.1897331>

Webb, M., Copes, H. and Hendricks, P.S. (2019). Narrative identity, rationality, and microdosing classic psychedelics. *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 70, pp.33–39. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2019.04.013>

Winstock, A.R., Maier, L.J., Zhuparris, A., Davies, E., Puljevic, C., Kuypers, K.P.C., Ferris, J.A. And Barratt, M.J. (2021). Global Drug Survey (GDS) 2021 Key Findings Report. [online] Available at: https://www.globaldrugsurvey.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Report2021_global.pdf

Appendix 2: Theme-wise summaries of the ten selected studies

Key:

+	Increased/improved/enhanced/more
-	Decreased/diminished/less
Green	Positives
Red	Negatives
Black & "•"	Neutral & Comments/Observations

Authors	Mental Health	Psychosocial and General Wellbeing	Cognitive Functioning	Others
Johnstad, 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Positive therapeutic effects - Anxiety - Depression - Side effects (as compared to other pharma options e.g. SSRIs) - Suicidal ideation - Manic bipolar depression - Symptoms of OCD & PTSD + Exacerbation of certain symptoms or conditions (e.g. hangovers, MH problems etc.) + Mood + Emotional stability & regulation + Control of feelings and reactions • Varied experiences – no one psychedelic worked the same for everyone or was effective – trial & error + comparison used to make personal decisions regarding MD regimen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Energy + Mood + Daily functioning + Connectedness & capacity to relate to other people + Openness & extraversion + Restlessness + Introspection + Meditative/contemplative mood + Pain management - Smoking + Aftereffects of MD (conflicting- some back to normal the next day, some experiencing an “afterglow”, while some feeling a change in energy levels or headaches, etc.) + Insomnia + Overstimulation and hyperactivity + Tension • Some combined micro and full doses (+ other drugs) for recreational purposes – mostly positive experiences but one reported a bad trip 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Cognitive ability + Daily functioning + Productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regimen: schedules, typology, dosage, etc. (research + experimentation) • Concerns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> negative experiences due to overdosing (e.g. mini-dose instead of microdose), uneasiness due to the uncertainty regarding long-term effects of MD, some experienced no effects or negative effects (and abandoned the practice) • Physiological effects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Symptoms of narcolepsy & migraines
Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Preference for using organic medicine & holistic methods for improving mental health - Depression - Anxiety - Impacts of trauma + Mood - Negative emotional states - Grief - Sadness - Melancholy + Already positive moods, attitudes & outlooks + Resilience + Optimism + Empathy + Calmness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Consistent with “smart living” + Importance of organic/natural living + Holistic healing + Healthier with less side effects (as compared to mainstream medicines) + Spirituality, self-help & mindfulness + Sociability + Mood + Sense of community & connectedness + Energy e.g. made waking up easier - Coffee intake throughout the day - Social anxiety or introversion - Symptoms associated with drug addiction - Heroin - Prescription opioids - Alcohol - Cigarettes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Productivity + Creativity + Motivation + Work satisfaction + Focus + Energy + Organisation & fulfilling plans/ goals + Efficiency + Ability to perform abstracts or difficult tasks + Self-actualisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • View of microdosers of themselves – conventional, rational, motivated towards self-improvement etc. • Safe procurement and regimen (schedule & dosage)- minimising risks (legal & from adverse effects) and being rational (based on research + self-experimentation) • Perceived danger = low • Concerns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal & adverse effects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Debilitating headaches - Menstrual cramps - Impacts of injuries e.g. MD aided emotional rehabilitation from a brain injury

<p>Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Depression - Anxiety - PTSD - ADHD + relief from mental health symptoms + feeling "normal" + Calmness + Mood + Emotional connection with oneself - Getting stuck in the cycle of worry & inertia - "Inner doubt" - fear of judgement - Over-analysing situation - Resolution or new pathways to healing + No mental health improvements + Anxiety (particularly social anxiety) + Extreme emotions - Control over emotions • Used as a self-managed maintenance therapy to replace antidepressants or other psychiatric medications – or as an adjunct to prescribed medications (less common) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Self-insight + Self-awareness + Self-acceptance + Reflection (on circumstances, areas & reasons for discontentment and strategies to affect change) + Mood + Brightness + Enthusiasm + "Perceptual enhancement of all you do" + Mindfulness + Feeling present + Ability to face situations/resilience + Connection to senses & emotions (experienced more fully) - Habits & behaviours they were unhappy with + Beneficial practices (e.g., healthier diet, weight loss, exercise and gym, ceasing or reducing substance use, improving sleep patterns, financial management) + Motivation to "stay on track" + Greater meaning and purpose + Social interactions + Interpersonal connections - Social anxiety - "Inner doubt" - fear of judgement - Over-analysing situations + self-confidence + Openness + Acceptance + unpleasant effects if dose was too high (nervousness, anxiety, feeling "too elevated", others e.g. visual distortions) + Difficulty in determining the right dose + Adverse psychological effects + Unpleasantness ("hangover effect" or feeling "weird" for a couple of days) • Effects were experienced stronger on days of MD but carried on to the following days 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Aligning work and study with life goals Cognitive performance + Focus + Productivity + Stamina + Capacity for learning + Creativity + Problem solving + Absorbing new information + Generating new ideas - Effort - Over-analysis - Procrastination - Anxiety + Motivation + Clarity in thinking + Effective prioritisation of tasks - Time-wasting activities - Cognitive barriers + Motivation + No cognitive improvements - Focus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dosing practices- adjustments to find their "sweet spot" & avoid experiencing psychedelic effects • Concerns/Risks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> withdrawing from medication without support, small body of evidence, variable effects – even when you take the same substance at the same schedule and dose, problems with= dosing, legality, purity/quality of substances, dependence, short-lived effects, unknown risks for long-term use • Physiological effects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Headaches + Fatigue + Nausea - Immune function + Sweating + Dilated pupils + Sleep problems + Strange dreams + Tinnitus + Shaking + Dizziness + Distracting sexual energy - Appetite + Joint/muscle tightness
<p>Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anxiety - Depression + Rare physical anxiety (physical sensations of anxiety) - Negative thoughts - Relaxed + Mood + Happier + Overwhelming with powerful emotions + Sensitive to peoples energy's/emotions + Stress/worries about legality and risks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Mindfulness + Understanding oneself - Control + Overactive brain/thoughts - Sleep + Relationships + Listening + Initiative + Confidence + Social effort - Social anxiety + Extra chatty or a bit too loud or exuberant in interactions + Healthy behaviours - Substance use (e.g. alcohol, cannabis) - Need for stimulants (e.g. coffee) - Negativity + Positive outlook on life (themselves & others) + Satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Problem solving + generating new ideas + Focus + Mental sharpness - "Noise" + Creativity + "Hangover effect" or "slightly cloudy head" + Overactive brain/thoughts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agency & rationale: intent to improve certain aspects of their lives, active choice, motivations for mental health, cognitive functioning, relationships, overall wellbeing etc., justified rationale (to explore benefits), based on research & systematic, comparisons, self-experimentation • Concerns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legality & risks

<p>Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Relief of symptoms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Neuropsychiatric conditions - Treatment resistant conditions - Depression (and long-standing major depression and otherwise hard to treat cases) - Anxiety - Catastrophizing thought patterns - Dysfunctional beliefs + Disease insight - PTSD - Bipolar disorder + Cognitive and social abilities of users with neuropsychiatric conditions (e.g., ADHD & ASD) - Constant evaluation/analysis etc. + Mood - Stress - Sadness - Anger - Other unwanted feelings + Emotional regulation + Evoking latent emotional content (e.g. trauma or things in the un/subconscious mind to process them) + Anxiety <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used as self-treatment when health care, prescribed treatments, or other methods were found insufficient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + States & senses + Confidence + Alterations of time perception + Feeling "Present" + Perceptual clarity + Sensory awareness + Quality of subjective experiences + Mood + Energy levels + "Drive" + Patience + Openness + Sense of groundedness and gratitude + Thoughtful insights + Transformation (psychospiritual changes) + Self-reflection + Personal orientation + Priorities + Habits + Desire to "live authentically" & with more connection with nature & care for the needs of self & others + Understanding of personal truths or core beliefs + Cognizant (of personal actions & psychological, psychosocial & lifestyle factors) + Self-confidence + Self-acceptance - Social unease + Empathy + Deeper connections in personal relationships + Trusting & adaptive approach to the "flow of life" + Connection with spiritual experiences & nature - Urge for unhealthy habits + "Presence" + Extraversion + Attendance + Persuasiveness + Influence others + Generate new relations or work-related opportunities - Problematic suffering + Discomfort + Noticeable affect at work (awkward) + Overly aware of bodily sensations + Overstimulation + Insomnia + Impulsivity - No pro-social effects + Introversion - Drug addiction (alcohol, narcotics, prescription drugs, and nicotine) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Abilities + Performance + Presence - Mental chatter + Focus + Flow + Perceptual clarity + Creativity + Productivity + Convergent & divergent thinking - Creative roadblocks/ writer's blocks + Enjoyment of work - Procrastination + Problem solving + Efficiency + "Presence" + Extraversion + Attendance + Persuasiveness + Influence others + Generate new relations or work-related opportunities + Leadership abilities + Adaptability & sensitivity to the needs & social feedback of co-workers - Procrastination + restlessness/ "jitters" - Focus + Hyper & sloppy - No productivity enhancement effects - Practical or problem-solving skills - Mechanical intelligence + Overstimulation + Insomnia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motives, expectations & context: self-treatment, self-optimisation, exploration, holistic approach, specific trends/lifestyle orientations • Approaches, strategies & dosage: hand-on procedures, mental preparations, strategies for optimal results, dosage & administration, effects of substances, precautions to minimise risks of unwanted effects • General viewpoints: what MD is, why & how it works, how it compared to other methods or medications, safety, cost-effectiveness, benefits, legality, stigma • Concerns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> mixed reports on the effects (positive, negative & null), legality, stigma • Most negative effects were experienced due to incorrect dosing • Physiological effects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paralysis and dyspraxia - Treatment-resistant cluster headaches + Discomfort + Noticeable affect at work (awkward) + Overly aware of bodily sensations + Gastrointestinal discomfort + Cramping + Body temperature + restlessness/ "jitters"
--------------------------------------	---	---	---	---

<p>Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Depression - Anxiety - Addiction (alcoholism) - Mood disorders + Mood + Happy/enjoyable - Stress + Stress + Clinical symptoms (e.g. anxiety & depersonalisation) • Used in combination/conjunction with therapy and meds et. to maintain effects • Some people might experience negative effects due to their internal states (anxious or depressed), it might amplify those feelings & trigger something beyond their control, leading to them not being able to handle them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Energy + Ability to take different perspectives + Personality + Growth + Social aptitude + Insight into life + Active + Mood + Lucid dreaming + Interpersonal interactions + Fluid social functioning + Deeper interpersonal connection + Quality of life + Self-acceptance + Appreciation for life + Awareness of themselves & their relationships (to others and the world) + Living in the present + Letting things go + Calm + Connection - Overthinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Productivity + Novel/creative thought + Schoolwork + Ability to take different perspectives - Motivation - Critical thinking + Clarity + Focus + Creativity + Reading comprehension + Spatial awareness + Abstract comprehension + Motivation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice: dosage, schedules etc., on its own or in combination (as part of a self-improvement regimen or with other performance-enhancement drugs) etc. • Positives: long-lasting benefits, few negative side-effects, safer, awareness, effects of different drugs • Concerns: scepticism about benefits, MD not for everyone, feeling "too good", i.e. hedonism rather than productivity, tolerance, effect of mindset, environment, set & setting, Some reports of no effects- probably due to miscalculations in dosage
<p>Hupli et al., 2019</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Depression - Anxiety + Existing severe anxiety + Mood + Emotional balance + Positive mental attitude 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Mood +Energy - Side-effects as compared to other performance-enhancement drugs + Senses (visual, auditory, touch etc.) + Calm/chill + Awareness + Introspection + Focus + Social interaction + Overall wellbeing + Workouts + Outlook on life + Personal development + Better sleep & eating habits + Exercise, yoga & meditation + Insomnia + Social performance + Coping strategy to deal with life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Creativity + Focus + Smoother thoughts + Mental clarity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of self-experimentation – lived experiences & measurements • Physiological effects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Heart rate - Physical capabilities (body feels heavy)
<p>Holm et al., 2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Social performance + Coping strategy to deal with life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Creativity + Work effectiveness + Academic performance + Focus - Focus (if dose too high) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerns: Placebo & medical evidence, lack of research • Microdosing not considered a psychedelic experience 	

<p>Prevete et al., 2021</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Anxiolysis - Substance abuse (e.g. amphetamine) - Addiction (marijuana, heroin, opioids & alcohol) - Depression - PTSD + Mood + Euphoria + Relaxation + Mild depression <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthier and safer than benzos & other meds for MH and pain etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Energy + Social interaction + Empathy - Drinking + Dysphoria + Apathy + Insomnia - Substance abuse (e.g. amphetamine) - Addiction (marijuana, heroin, opioids & alcohol) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Productivity - Fatigue + Concentration + Focus + Creativity - Motivation + Apathy + Attention + Drowsiness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negatives usually occurs when you use kratom multiple times a day or use more than you should • Concerns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addiction, dependence with tolerance, withdrawal syndrome, death from overdosing/combinations etc. • Physiological effects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acute/chronic/extreme pain management + Sexual desire - Sleep problems + Nausea + Headaches + Sedation + Appetite + Weakness + Sweating - Sexual desire + Dizziness + Weight loss
<p>Askew & Williams, 2021</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anxiety - Stress - Depression + Mood - Low mood 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Self-improvement + Self-discovery + Consciousness + Spirituality + Mood + Connectivity + Intimacy + Energy + Sleep + Daily functioning + Higher meaning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Alertness + Creativity + Cognition + Work + Focus + Learning + Understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physiological effects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Pain relief + Movement

Appendix 3: Theme-wise anecdotal accounts from participants in the ten selected studies

Depression and Anxiety

"I have had very positive results from infrequent psilocybin microdosing. I have found fast and relatively long-lasting relief from depression and social anxiety doing this, as compared to other pharmaceutical options I've been offered such as SSRIs [selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors], and without the intolerable (for me) side effects." (Johnstad, 2018)

"I have had major depression and anxiety for over 15 years and nothing has worked for me. I've tried multiple medications, therapies, exercises, etc. I read a study recently that microdosing can help reset the brain and cure depression. Out of desperation I decided to give this a shot." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

"I have treatment resistant depression and PTSD w/dissociation (both diagnosed). I'm prescribed Dexametridine and a Selegiline patch daily to keep myself immersed and grounded in the world instead of curled up in bed for weeks at a time. The LSD is a supplemental therapy that my psychiatrist gave me a wink wink to go ahead and use. It's to increase abstract thinking and emotional responsiveness in the presence of such strong, overriding stimulants." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

"The ability to feel sad without getting depressed is exactly what I've been experiencing. As someone that suffered a lot from anxiety and depression it's amazing how ... normal I feel now" (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

"I went from being in a pretty bad crisis state to normal in a day. Can't say it's that effective for everyone, but it's been amazing and life-changing for me. Therapist was prepared to put me on some serious meds, I came in and shocked the hell out of her with how level I was." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

"To me it's [psilocybin] usefulness is also tied to the fact that it is effects can be felt almost immediately compared to traditional pharmaceutical anti-depressants and even many holistic ones" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

"I don't know if you know this but when you're depressed your vision actually changes colour so you see life in more of a grayscale and when I microdosed that disappeared, everything was brighter again" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

"Microdosing LSD has been the best thing that happened in my life. Dealing with serious depression for 35 years... it's now GONE!" (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)

"Want to point out that I started my microdosing experiment with psilocybin mushrooms and therein got relief from depression and alcoholism. I microdosed every fourth day for three months, then continued occasionally as needed for re-emerging symptoms of depression for nearly a year. I recently switched to LSD in hopes of increased energy as well as antidepressant effect. I prefer LSD because of the increased energy it gives me and intend to continue microdosing LSD indefinitely." (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

"The best period of my life seemed while I microdosed semi-frequently, my psychiatric problems (depression, anxiety and drug mis-use) were diminished. I stayed sober, active, happy and created a lot" (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

"If it's not for Kratom he suffers such bad depression" (Prevete et al., 2021)

"It also has kind of benefit of antidepressant" (Prevete et al., 2021)

"It was found to have an acute ability to reduce anxiety" (Prevete et al., 2021)

"People used it as alternative to anti-anxiety medication" (Prevete et al., 2021)

"It also has kind of benefit as Anxiolytic" (Prevete et al., 2021)

"It has really helped me cope with my depression, actually. It really got me out of a hole I was in, in the lead up to Christmas, I was having medical procedures and I would have a mushroom trip every two weeks, eight times in total, it really pulled me out of a really bad depression that I was sinking into. It has been huge actually and I think it helped me cope with hospital and my life being on hold, because my life has been on hold for nearly two years." (Askew & Williams, 2021)

"I noticed that after a certain point, the benefits fade, and microdosing instead serves to exacerbate my mental health problems." (Johnstad, 2018)

"If I have a day where I'm doing something new or working around new people, and thus have to be more social, then I won't microdose. That's mostly due to social anxiety sometimes being exacerbated by microdosing." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)

"Very very rarely if I get the type of physical anxiety [physical sensations of anxiety] it will feel worse than normal ...but those instances are very rare" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

"Overwhelmed by those powerful emotions...But that didn't happen often...It had both benefits and disadvantages" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)

"You do feel a higher degree of connectedness with yourself, to the point where if you do have anxious thoughts or if there's something you're worrying about it is possible for that worry to be enhanced." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)

"I feel that microdosing has a lot to do with how you feel inside at the moment and/or what you wish to achieve at the moment. I feel that psychedelics amplify, in a way, our current feelings/needs/wants. SO if people are feeling depressed or anxious, I believe that they shouldn't do it if they don't know what they are getting into, because for some weak hearted, it might trigger something that will be beyond their control. Although overall I am definitely convinced of the therapeutic power of psychedelics, psilocybin mushrooms to be exact, but I also know that some people cannot handle them." (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)

<p>Mood and Emotions</p> <p>"I had a great day! Very calm mind, emotionally in balance" (Johnstad, 2018)</p> <p>"I feel more open to other people. At home with my family, I feel better equipped to deal with disagreement, and my emotional reactions are less automatic. My mood improves, and I have better contact with my feelings and less restlessness. I more often take the initiative to talk." (Johnstad, 2018)</p> <p>I definitely felt an afterglow just like if you dose high enough for an actual psychedelic experience. (Johnstad, 2018)</p> <p>"It's [microdosing] like hacking your brain, you know? Like being a better you. ... I feel like you're generally happier, more upbeat, kind of more open minded also." (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)</p> <p>"I become more optimistic and things didn't get to me as much or bother me. I was more inclined to, I guess, laugh and smile" (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)</p> <p>"I decided to start microdosing again because I've been having trouble keeping my emotions under control (namely anger and frustration) and it has taken a noticeable toll not only on my work but also in my friendships" (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"a dose of 4 to 5 µg puts me in a much more euphoric" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"...it improves your mood and makes you euphoric" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"Euphoric enough that you feel like going out and doing things" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"I feel very content, like I'm covered with a warm blanket" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"It can make someone feel very relaxed and chill" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"[microdosing] helped me get hold of my thoughts in same fashion meditation helps...And really dive deeper as far as I could to sort out things that I didn't need anymore and basically understand myself from a fundamental stand point...In sense I was a psychologist to myself...Free consultation whenever I needed...Tapping into my own "demons" was a rewarding experience" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)</p> <p>"a bit chill, a bit calm, like I had one little tiny drag of a joint" (Hupfl et al., 2019)</p> <p>"Overall not much has improved my mood still fluctuates and I'm still fairly antisocial." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"For me, there can be times when microdosing makes it more difficult to shake off feelings of fear and being unsafe. I've noticed this more with mushrooms than LSD." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p>	<p>Natural and Holistic Approach</p> <p>"I'm a plant person. My wife and I have a garden, we grow a bunch of food, we're both naturalist leaning in our views about medications and doctors and hospitals and healthy eating and stuff, so if we can grow our medicine rather than pay someone for an encapsulated synthesized fake version of that then I'm going to do that." (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)</p> <p>"I am a big self-help kind of person, so I feel like a lot of that like spiritual, self-help, Buddhist, yogi type stuff and hallucinogens, go hand in hand well." (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)</p> <p>"I was already doing things to become less anxious and depressed, and to have more confidence. Things like yoga, meditation, eating right, working out, and doing personal development. But once I added mushrooms, it was like all of that, put on steroids." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"This world is plagued with junk food, porn, materialism, jealousy, and all these things. I think mushrooms connect us to a much simpler ancient way of viewing the world." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"did not seem to be a drug, but an herbal medicine" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"a safe natural substance" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"It has been used for hundreds of years as a natural traditional medicine" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"I think it's much more healthy and safe than Benzodiazepine" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p>
--	--

<p>Other Mental Health conditions</p>	<p>"The huge benefit I've noticed is that I'm starting to process my life/trauma differently. I started dosing because I felt like I had hit a wall in my treatment and was tired of feeling so haunted and like my whole sense of self and life were dictated by trauma." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"I've been taking [ADHD] medication daily for the past 10 years, I always had an issue with concentrating. Microdosing ... let me get into that flow state and get all my work done in one sitting." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"I'm bipolar and used anti-depressives my entire life. The only medicine that works for me is Psilocybin mushrooms. I microdose and grow my own now. I have never felt better." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"It can help people with Asperger's learn to socialize without killing their love of science. At least that is what LSD and DMT did for me" (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"Instead of blunting our emotional response to trauma that we've had in the past, the trauma starts to come up, and we have to look at it and integrate it in a way that helps us to become a more healthy self." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"Adderall has this feeling of like forcing you to focus, whereas, with LSD, it's more like you want to." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"I had tremendous success in recently treating decades of aftermath of long term abuse, trauma and loss with full dose psychedelic medicines. I am microdosing now for maintenance in conjunction with talk therapy and it has been nothing short of miraculous for me." (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)</p> <p>"I noticed that after a certain point, the benefits fade, and microdosing instead serves to exacerbate my mental health problems." (Johnstad, 2018)</p> <p>"I actually feel when I MD that I am much less organized and everything seems to distract me. I feel much better on my regular dose of Adderall [ADHD medication]." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p>
<p>Social Functioning, Relationships and Empathy</p>	<p>"Before I started microdosing I was very, very down, upset, depressed, not leaving my room. And then I started microdosing and I felt motivated to start studying, do my homework all day long. I was going out, talking to all my friends, interacting with other people. I feel a more intimate connection with them." (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)</p> <p>"I would notice myself being more outgoing and just, I would hear myself talk and go like, 'Wow! I wouldn't normally have said something like that!'" (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)</p> <p>"euphoria and a general sort of vague feeling of community and connectedness" (Webb, Copes and Hendricks, 2019)</p> <p>"I get a bit anxious in social settings and when having to speak to groups of people. I find I just connect better with everyone ... when I'm microdosing. It's a hard slog if I'm not. I am also better at small talk in social settings and far more engaged with the people I'm hanging out with. Some weeks I just need all the extra support I can get and I find microdosing LSD the best way of getting it." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"I still have a notable inner doubt that holds me back at times from acting and interacting the way I truly want to. On microdose days, that's just nonexistent. I'm far more exuberant and outgoing, and I clearly see that attitude reflected in the people I talk to." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"I feel more empathetic and have an easier time being a "good person", especially to those I can joyously call my friends ... If I'm engaged in an interaction with someone else, I'm largely at ease and my unfiltered self is put forward with almost no conscious effort." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"I have gained so much confidence it's crazy. I have a new career lined up. I am sociable, I am happy to speak up for myself. I don't even recognise the person that I was!... No social anxiety... For the first time ever" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)</p> <p>"Microdosing is a pretty good way to get out of your shell and socialize with people, in my opinion. I'm not usually the one to drive conversation out of people, but on LSD it's almost too easy not to." (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)</p> <p>"socialization becomes more unsuppressed and effortless" (Prevete et al., 2021)</p> <p>"Overall not much has improved my mood still fluctuates and I'm still fairly antisocial." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"If I have a day where I'm doing something new or working around new people, and thus have to be more social, then I won't microdose. That's mostly due to social anxiety sometimes being exacerbated by microdosing." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"Apart from being extra chatty on the days I take it, I can't think of any disadvantages" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)</p> <p>"a bit too loud or exuberant in interactions" (Ryan, Copello and Fox, 2023)</p> <p>"Psychedelics tended to make me depersonalized long after I took them. Even in microdoses." (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)</p>

<p>Self-insight, Acceptance and Mindfulness</p>	<p>"I get bright moods, good introspection in meditation, and a generally meditative, contemplative mood." (Johnstad, 2018)</p> <p>"Microdosing has shown me that I normally paint my life a lot grayer than it needs to be." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"Would have the occasional wave of anxiety and negative thoughts, but embraced them for what they were ... it seemed to release them." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"Since dosing I've become more in-touch with what I feel and as a result that helps me make decisions about getting to where I want to be." (Lea, Amada and Jungaberle, 2019)</p> <p>"I was able to just "be" instead of constantly evaluating/analyzing/talking with myself about the way things are, and that's a feeling that's been elusive in my normal state." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"Yes, microdosing can be performance-enhancing, but it also increases the odds you're going to do the kind of work that can, not only be of deeper alignment with yourself, but also work that will be of benefit to people beyond yourself." (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"They've been able to show me who I am" (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"Microdosing revealed to me parts of my personality, my nature, that I wasn't proud of and wasn't easy to face" (Andersson and Kjellgren, 2019)</p> <p>"I believe the greatest thing I learnt from microdosing was to stop trying to solve problems I perceived about myself and just accept them for what they were. Accept myself for who I am, relax, stop overthinking everything because at the end of the day none of this matters so you may as well enjoy yourself however you see fit." (Petranker, Kim and Anderson, 2022)</p>
--	---

Appendix 4: Example of preliminary describing coding/notes

Powerful substances in tiny amounts (Johnstad, 2018)

1 Microdose regimen Respondents generally regarded microdosing as being compatible with most
 2 everyday activities. Some would microdose in the mornings of workdays, while others preferred to
 3 limit this activity to afternoons and non-working days. The most commonly used psychedelics for
 4 microdosing were psilocybin-containing “magic mushrooms” and lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD).
 5 There were also reports of microdosing experiences with Salvia divinorum, Amanita muscaria,
 6 Peganum harmala (Syrian rue), Echinopsis pachanoi (San Pedro cactus), N,N-dimethyltryptamine
 7 (DMT), 2,5-Dimethoxy-4-methylamphetamine (DOM), and cannabis. Some users had experimented
 8 with a broad range of psychedelic substances, while others had limited this use to one specific
 9 psychedelic: The only traditional psychedelic I have microdosed is mushrooms. I find this to be
 10 extremely beneficial spiritually, physically, and mentally but have no experience with other
 11 traditional psychedelics as a basis for comparison. (ID14) I’ve had good success with Amanita as a
 12 daily tonic for wintertime blues. (ID13) Doses were usually constrained to about a tenth of a full
 13 dose. For LSD, this amounted to somewhere between 10 and 25 mcg, and for Psilocybe cubensis
 14 mushrooms to 0.1–0.3 g. Some reported taking up to a quarter of a full dose, but this was usually
 15 regarded as a mini-dose rather than a microdose, and was not found to be compatible with work and
 16 everyday activities. Respondents sometimes found it difficult to specify the exact dose they were
 17 taking. Some indicated that their microdose regimen was informed by extant literature on
 18 psychedelic microdosing. These were some typical statements about dosage: I normally cut up a
 19 single blotter of 100 or 150 mcg into 8 pieces, giving microdoses in the range of 12.5 to 18.75 mcg.
 20 (ID38) I have microdosed frequently, generally following Fadiman’s recommendation of 1/10th of a
 21 dose every four days. (ID33) I dose 10 mcg LSD twice per week. I came to this amount by
 22 administering doses at 5 mcg intervals within the following range [5–25]. I have found that 10 mcg is
 23 the most beneficial. Any more and I’m a little too impressionable to distraction, any less and there’s
 24 no benefit. (ID39) For experienced microdosers, the practice was usually regarded as a cyclic activity,
 25 with microdosing periods lasting from a few weeks to a few months. Within such a period, the
 26 respondents typically dosed one to three times per week, although some reported dosing on a daily
 27 basis. Less experienced users reported occasional experiments without any stable regimen. Dosing a
 28 few times a week did not seem to result in significant build up of tolerance (abatement of positive
 29 effects), although with one reported exception for DOM. There were conflicting reports on tolerance
 30 build up from daily microdosing and about the impact of microdose tolerance on full doses. Some
 31 frequent microdose users experienced a build up of tolerance, while others found no such effect: In
 32 the last year, I have been experimenting with LSD microdoses quite frequently. But in the past two
 33 months, I have gone from taking it every third day to every day. What amazes me is the fact that I
 34 don’t seem to feel any tolerance build up at all. (ID38) Surprisingly, a one-day break is sufficient for
 35 avoiding tolerance. This went against the conventional wisdom online suggesting that a few days in
 36 between was necessary. Dosing on consecutive days saw tolerance, then headaches. (ID39)
 37 Experienced therapeutic effects Respondents generally agreed that proper microdoses (about a
 38 tenth of a full dose) of LSD and psilocybin did not result in any intoxication. Some respondents
 39 experienced no effect at all from microdosing, and therefore abandoned the practice after a few
 40 attempts, but the majority reported some effect that they regarded as positive. The most commonly
 41 described effects were health related, with a benign influence noted especially on states of
 42 depression and anxiety: I have had very positive results from infrequent psilocybin microdosing. I
 43 have found fast and relatively long-lasting relief from depression and social anxiety doing this, as
 44 compared to other pharmaceutical options I’ve been offered such as SSRIs [selective serotonin
 45 reuptake inhibitors], 44 Nordic Studies on Alcohol and Drugs 35(1) and without the intolerable (for
 46 me) side effects. (ID29) The best relief I ever had was in the 0.1 g to 0.2 g range of Psilocybe

1/4th of a full dose

Reply

SM Scheza Mudasser (MSc Ment...
Mini-dose = not compatible

Reply

SM Scheza Mudasser (MSc Ment...
People faced difficulty in identifying the exact dosage

Reply

SM Scheza Mudasser (MSc Ment...
Regimen may be informed by lit/research + be modified based on personal experiences, understanding & preference - pretty varied as well

Reply

SM Scheza Mudasser (MSc Ment...
For experienced users - may be cyclic - ranging from few weeks to few months

Reply

SM Scheza Mudasser (MSc Ment...
Varied regimen - 3/week or everyday

Reply

SM Scheza Mudasser (MSc Ment...
For less experienced users - may be occasional experiments - no specific pattern/regimen followed